

COMPARISON OF EFFECTIVENESS OF PASSIVE STRETCHINGS VERSUS NERVE MOBILIZATIONS ON PLANTAR FLEXOR SPASTICITY, ANKLE ROM, AND GAIT VELOCITY IN SUBACUTE STROKE SUBJECTS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction:

Stroke is a major cause of long-term disability worldwide, and often results in motor impairments such as spasticity, especially in the plantar flexor muscles of the lower limb. This spasticity can limit ankle movement, affect balance, and impair walking ability, particularly during the subacute phase of recovery. To manage these impairments, physiotherapy interventions such as passive stretching and nerve mobilization are widely utilized. Passive stretching aims to reduce muscle stiffness and maintain joint flexibility, while nerve mobilization targets neural tissue mobility to relieve tension and improve functional movement.

Aim:

The study aims at evaluating the comparison of effectiveness of passive stretching versus nerve mobilizations on plantar flexor spasticity, ankle rom, and gait velocity in subacute stroke subjects.

Method

The data of 30 subjects with plantar flexor spasticity with a mean age between 45 to 65 years were included in the study based on the inclusion criteria. The subjects were divided into Group-A and Group-B groups. The group A received both the passive stretchings and Conventional treatment. In contrast, the group B received nerve mobilizations, and Conventional treatment at a rate of 6 days per week, 1 hour a day over a total duration of 4 weeks. The Modified Ashworth Scale, universal goniometer and Timed up go test were measured the outcomes.

Results

The mean age of participants in Group A (Passive Stretching) was 56.9 years (± 7.7) and in Group B (Nerve Mobilization) was 54.6 years (± 7.0). Pre-treatment mean MAS scores were 2.53 (± 0.51) in Group A and 2.47 (± 0.51) in Group B. Post-treatment, the MAS scores reduced to 1.87 (± 0.83) in Group A and 0.60 (± 0.50) in Group B. Ankle dorsiflexion ROM improved from 3.93° (± 0.79) to 8.73° (± 0.96) in Group A and from 3.80° (± 0.77) to 10.93° (± 1.16) in Group B. Gait velocity decreased from 27.03 seconds (± 1.22) to 21.96 seconds (± 1.12) in Group A and from 28.07 seconds (± 2.82) to 18.96 seconds (± 2.00) in Group B. Between-group comparisons showed significant differences favoring the nerve mobilization group for all outcomes ($p < 0.001$), with very large effect sizes indicating greater treatment effectiveness.

Conclusion

This study shows that combined nerve mobilization and Conventional treatment was effective in decreasing the Plantar Flexor spasticity and Gait velocity in subacute stroke subjects.

Keywords

Ischemic stroke, passive stretchings, nerve mobilizations, Modified Ashworth Scale, Ankle ROM and Gait velocity.

INTRODUCTION

Stroke is a leading cause of mortality and long-term disability worldwide (1,2). It results from a disruption of blood supply to the brain, leading to neuronal injury and brain tissue damage. This disruption can occur either due to an obstruction of cerebral blood flow, known as ischaemic stroke, or due to the rupture of cerebral blood vessels causing bleeding into or around brain tissue, known as haemorrhagic stroke (1). Ischaemic stroke is typically caused by thrombotic or embolic arterial occlusion, whereas haemorrhagic stroke includes intracerebral and subarachnoid haemorrhage, both of which result in acute intracranial bleeding and increased intracranial pressure (2).

Motor impairments are among the most common functional deficits following stroke.

Damage to motor cortex regions or descending motor pathways can result in hemiparesis, which is weakness on one side of the body, or in severe cases, hemiplegia, a complete loss of motor control on one side (3). Patients may also experience abnormal muscle tone, impaired coordination, balance difficulties, spasticity, and involuntary movements, all of which

significantly limit mobility and daily functioning (3). These impairments greatly affect independence and quality of life.

The burden of stroke is further compounded by high disability and recurrence rates. Within the first 12 months, disability levels range from 11.1% to 29.2%, and a large proportion of survivors continue to experience motor, speech, swallowing, cognitive, and other functional impairments (4). Recurrence

remains a major challenge, with overall rates around 5.7%, reaching up to 11.65% in cases of cerebral infarction (5).

Globally, stroke imposes a substantial economic and societal burden, with costs estimated to exceed US \$890 billion and disproportionately affecting low- and lower-middle-income countries. Stroke remains one of the leading causes of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs), accounting for millions of deaths and over 11 million DALYs annually (6)

Nerve mobilization, also known as neurodynamics or neural mobilization, is a manual therapy technique designed to restore the normal mobility, elasticity, and physiological function of the nervous system. It is based on the understanding that the nervous system is a continuous, dynamic structure that must move and adapt in coordination with surrounding tissues during functional activities. Any restriction, irritation, or entrapment of peripheral nerves can cause pain, altered sensation, restricted range of motion, and functional limitations.(43)

The process of lengthening the soft tissues of the muscles is called stretching. Stretching can be performed manually by the subject or therapist, or with the aid of external tools such as tilt tables, splints, or casts (44). Stretching decreases spasticity by reducing motor neuron excitability through sustained compression and extension on the cutaneous receptors, joint receptors, muscle spindles, and Golgi tendon organs (GTOs).

AIM OF THE STUDY

To compare the effect of passive stretching versus nerve mobilizations on plantar flexor spasticity, ankle ROM and gait velocity in subacute stroke subjects.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To evaluate the effect of Passive Stretching's of plantar flexors in subacute stroke subjects on spasticity by using Modified Ashworth Scale(MAS), on Ankle Range of Motion by using universal goniometer, on Gait Velocity by using Timed Up Go Test(TUG).
2. To evaluate the effect of Nerve Mobilizations in subacute stroke subjects on spasticity by using Modified Ashworth Scale(MAS), on Ankle Range of Motion by using universal goniometer, on Gait Velocity by using Timed Up Go Test(TUG).
3. To compare the effect of Passive Stretching versus Nerve Mobilizations on plantar flexor spasticity, Ankle ROM, Gait Velocity by using Modified Ashworth Scale (MAS), Universal Goniometer, Timed Up Go Test(TUG) in subjects with Subacute Stroke.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

METHOD:

- Study design: Randomized control trail
- Sampling Technique: Purposive sampling method.
- Randomization method: Simple random sampling by lottery method
- Sample size (N): 30 {Group-A = (n)15 subjects, Group-B = (n)15 subjects}.
- Study setting :
 - College of physiotherapy, General ward, SVIMS.
 - Sri Venkateswara ayurvedic hospital.
- Study duration: 6 months
- Treatment duration:(40 minutes/session,5 sessions/week for a duration of 4 weeks.)
- Ethical code : **IEC No.1772, Date : 13.03.2025**
- **CTRI NO: REGISTRATION NO: CTRI/2025/06/088359**

MATERIALS:

Following materials were used for the evaluation and intervention

Stopwatch, Measuring tape, Cones, Universal Goniometer.

Ice pack, Manipulation couch, Drape sheet , Pillows, Stepper.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Subjects of 45-65 years of age
- Subjects with ischemic stroke(Unilateral stroke affecting on either side)
- Both males and females
- Subjects with MMSE: 24-30
- VCG(voluntary control grading) >3
- MAS (Modified Ashworth scale) : GRADE 2
- Subjects who have ability to stand without support for 1 min.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Any other neurological deficits as multiple sclerosis, Parkinson's disease
- Subjects with visual and sensory deficits
- Mental retardation
- Any musculoskeletal disorders like OA, ligament injuries
- No cognitive deficits
- Recurrent hemiplegia
- Bilateral Hemiplegia

INTERVENTION

The study was performed after getting approval from **IEC No.1774**. All subjects who met the inclusion criteria were included in the study after subjects received a thorough explanation of the procedure. Written consent was then obtained from the subjects. The subjects were allocated to 2 groups, group A and group B in 1:1 ratio with 15 in each group.

Group A (Passive stretchings)	Group B (Nerve mobilizations)
Passive stretchings: to triceps surae (gastrocnemius and soleus muscles)	Nerve mobilizations: Posterior tibial nerve mobilizations:

<p>Treatment duration: 5 repetitions, 60–80 sec hold time, 6 sessions/week, 4 weeks, 1 session/day</p> <p>Treatment Time: 20 minutes per session</p> <p>Conventional treatment:</p> <p>Cryotherapy = 2 to 3min. (cryotherapy was given after each repetition of passive stretching).</p> <p>Weight-bearing exercises consisted of 3 repetitions, with a 15-20 second hold time, performed 6 sessions per week, for 4 weeks</p> <p>Treatment duration: 15 -20 minutes/session, 6 sessions/week for a duration of 4 weeks.</p>	<p>Treatment Duration: 5sets of 10 repetitions, 1 min rest, 5 sessions/week, 4 weeks, 1 session/day</p> <p>Treatment Time: 20 minutes per session</p> <p>Conventional treatment:</p> <p>Cryotherapy = 2 to 3min. (Cryotherapy will be given after each repetition of nerve mobilization).</p> <p>Weight-bearing exercises consisted of 3 repetitions, with a 15-20 second hold time, performed 5 sessions per week, for 4 weeks</p> <p>Treatment duration: 15 -20 minutes/session, 6 sessions/week for a duration of 4 weeks.</p>
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STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

RESULTS :

Descriptive statistics :

Baseline evaluation was done for the subjects in Groups A and B by using the Modified Ashworth Scale, universal goniometer and Timed up go test. Subjects have undergone the intervention for 4 weeks and post-test evaluation was done by using the above measures and documented the findings.

TABLE 5: Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of participants in group a and group b

VARIABLES	GROUP A (n=15) MEAN ± SD	GROUP B (n=15) MEAN ± SD	P- VALUE
AGE(YRS)	56.9±7.7	54.6 ± 7.0	0.396
GENDER (MALE:FEMALE)	8/7	9/6	0.713 (chi-square)
VCG SCORE	4.47 ± 0.51	4.47 ±0.51	0.726
MMSE SCORE	26.87 ± 1.68	27 ±1.9	0.842

The table shows that there was no significant difference between Group A and Group B in terms of age, gender, VCG score, or MMSE score at the start of the study. The average age was similar between the groups (Group A: 56.9 ± 7.7 years; Group B: 54.6 ± 7.0 years, $p = 0.396$). The male-to-female ratio was also comparable (Group A: 8 males and 7 females; Group B: 9 males and 6 females, $p = 0.713$). Both groups had the same mean VCG score (4.47 ± 0.51 , $p = 0.726$) and similar MMSE scores (Group A: 26.87 ± 1.68 ; Group B: 27 ± 1.9 , $p = 0.842$). These findings indicate that the groups were well-matched at baseline, ensuring that any differences observed after the intervention are likely due to the treatment rather than pre-existing differences.

TABLE : Within group analysis of mean values of mas, ankle rom(df) and gait velocity in group a

GROUP	OUTCOME	PRE (n=15) MEAN± SD	POST (n=15) MEAN ±SD	MEAN DIFFERNCE	t - VALUE	P- VALUE
A	MAS	2.53 ± 0.51	1.87 ± 0.83	0.66	4.18	0.00
A	Ankle ROM (DF)	3.93 ± 0.79	8.73 ± 0.96	4.8	17.17	0.00
A	TUG test (sec)	27.03 ± 1.22	21.96 ± 1.12	5.24	16.77	0.00

In Group A, there was a clear improvement after the treatment. The spasticity (MAS) score reduced from 2.53 to 1.87, showing less muscle tightness. The ankle movement (dorsiflexion ROM) increased from 3.93 degrees to 8.73 degrees, meaning better ankle flexibility. The time taken to do the TUG test got shorter, from 27.03 seconds to 21.96 seconds, showing better walking and balance. All these changes were statistically significant ($p = 0.00$), which means the treatment is effective.

TABLE 7: Within group analysis of mean values of mas, ankle rom (df) and tug test in group b

In Group B, there was a significant improvement after the treatment. The MAS (Modified

GROUP	OUTCOME	PRE (n=15) MEAN± SD	POST (n=15) MEAN ±SD	MEAN DIFFERNCE	t - VALUE	P- VALUE
B	MAS	2.47 ± 0.51	0.60 ± 0.50	1.87	20.54	0.00
B	ROM (DF)	3.80 ± 0.77	10.93 ± 1.16	7.13	27.89	0.00
B	Tug test	28.07 ± 2.82	18.96 ± 2.00	9.11	17.32	0.00

Ashworth Scale) score dropped from 2.47 ± 0.51 before treatment to 0.60 ± 0.50 after treatment, showing a large reduction in spasticity, with a mean difference of 1.87 ($t = 20.54, p = 0.00$). The ankle dorsiflexion range of motion (ROM) also improved greatly, increasing from 3.80 ± 0.77 degrees to 10.93 ± 1.16 degrees, with a mean difference of 7.13 ($t = 27.89, p = 0.00$). These results show that the intervention given to Group B was highly effective in reducing spasticity and increasing ankle flexibility.

TABLE : Between group analysis of mas, ankle rom (df) and tug test in group a and group b

OUTCOME	GROUP A (MEAN \pm SD)	GROUP B (MEAN \pm SD)	t - VALUE	P - VALUE
MAS	1.87 ± 0.83	0.60 ± 0.50	5.027	0.00
Ankle ROM (DF)	8.73 ± 0.96	10.93 ± 1.16	5.648	0.00
Tug test (sec)	21.96 ± 1.12	18.96 ± 2.00	4.904	0.00

When comparing Group A and Group B after the treatment, Group B showed better results in all outcomes. The MAS (Modified Ashworth Scale) score was lower in Group B (0.60 ± 0.50) compared to Group A (1.87 ± 0.83), showing that Group B had less spasticity ($t = 5.027, p = 0.00$). The ankle dorsiflexion ROM was higher in Group B (10.93 ± 1.16) than in Group A (8.73 ± 0.96), meaning Group B had greater ankle flexibility ($t = 5.648, p = 0.00$). The TUG (Timed Up and Go) test time was shorter in Group B (18.96 ± 2.00 seconds) than in Group A (21.96 ± 1.12 seconds), indicating better mobility and functional performance ($t = 4.904, p = 0.00$). All differences were statistically significant, showing that the nerve mobilization intervention given to Group B was more effective than the passive stretching intervention given to Group A.

Effect size calculation

TABLE : Comparison of outcome measures between group a and group b groups with effect sizes (cohen’s d).

Outcome	Passive Stretching (MEAN ± SD)	Nerve Mobilization (MEAN ± SD)	Pooled SD	Cohen’s D	Interpretation
MAS	1.87 ± 0.83	0.6 ± 0.5	0.684	1.86	Very large
Ankle ROM(DF)	8.73 ± 0.96	10.93 ± 1.16	1.065	2.07	Very large
TUG test	21.96 ± 1.12	18.96 ± 2.0	1.62	1.85	Very large

The table shows a comparison of outcomes between the Passive Stretching group and the Nerve Mobilization group, along with the effect size (Cohen’s D). For all three outcomes — MAS, ankle dorsiflexion ROM, and TUG test — the Cohen’s D values are very large (all above 1.8), indicating strong effects. Specifically, the MAS score was much lower in the Nerve Mobilization group (0.6 ± 0.5) than in the Passive Stretching group (1.87 ± 0.83), with a large effect size (Cohen’s D = 1.86). Ankle dorsiflexion ROM was higher in the Nerve Mobilization group (10.93 ± 1.16) compared to the Passive Stretching group (8.73 ± 0.96), with a large effect size (Cohen’s D = 2.07). The TUG test time was shorter in the Nerve Mobilization group (18.96 ± 2.0 seconds) than in the Passive Stretching group (21.96 ± 1.12 seconds), with a large effect size (Cohen’s D = 1.85). These results suggest that nerve mobilization led to significantly greater improvements than passive stretching in reducing spasticity, increasing ankle range of motion, and improving functional mobility.

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to compare the effectiveness of passive stretching and nerve mobilization techniques on plantar flexor spasticity, ankle dorsiflexion range of motion (ROM), and gait velocity in sub-acute stroke patients. Thirty ischemic stroke subjects aged 45–65 years were randomly allocated into two groups. Group A received passive stretching with conventional therapy, while Group B received nerve mobilization combined with

conventional therapy. Treatment was provided for four weeks (six sessions per week). Outcome measures included the Modified Ashworth Scale (MAS), ankle dorsiflexion ROM, and the Timed Up and Go (TUG) test. Both groups showed statistically significant improvements; however, Group B demonstrated greater reductions in spasticity and superior gains in ankle ROM and gait velocity. The MAS score improved to a mean of 0.6 ± 0.5 in the nerve mobilization group compared to 1.87 ± 0.83 in the passive stretching group (Cohen's $d = 1.86$). These findings are consistent with previous studies reporting that neural mobilization reduces spasticity more effectively than passive stretching (Ansari et al., 2020; Babatunde et al., 2020) (10). Similarly, Ellakany et al. (2021) demonstrated that tibial nerve mobilization significantly decreases lower limb hypertonia compared to conventional therapy alone (9). Improvements in ankle dorsiflexion ROM were also greater in Group B ($10.93^\circ \pm 1.16$) compared to Group A ($8.73^\circ \pm 0.96$), supporting earlier findings that neurodynamic techniques enhance joint mobility by improving neural gliding and reducing intraneural restrictions (Sharma VK et al., 2021; Kumar SP et al., 2019) (11,12). Furthermore, Group B showed faster TUG performance (18.96 ± 2.0 sec) than Group A (21.96 ± 1.12 sec), aligning with Prasanna K et al. (2021) and Zhang Y et al. (2022), who reported improved gait efficiency and dynamic balance following nerve mobilization (13). Hyong et al. (2020) also highlighted that nerve mobilization enhances neuromuscular coordination and gait performance when combined with functional training (14). The findings of this study are consistent with Saleh et al. (2022), who concluded that passive stretching provides only short-term relief, whereas nerve mobilization results in more sustained and clinically meaningful improvements in spasticity and function (15). Therefore, the study supports the acceptance of the alternate hypothesis that nerve mobilization produces greater improvements in spasticity, ankle ROM, and gait performance in sub-acute stroke patients.

CONCLUSION

The present study concluded that nerve mobilization along with Conventional treatment was found to be more effective compared to passive stretching and Conventional treatment on improving Plantar flexor Spasticity, Ankle ROM and Gait velocity in Subjects with subacute stroke. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

Despite promising findings, this study has limitations. The small sample size and short intervention period may limit generalizability. Long-term effects and carryover effects after the intervention period were not assessed. Future research should include larger multicentric trials with longer follow-ups and advanced gait analysis to validate and expand on these findings.

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